

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Edited by

Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

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by
IKSAD GLOBAL PUBLISHING HOUSE

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IKSAD GLOBAL Publications – 2022©

Issued: 02.12.2022

ISBN:978-625-6380-19-6

CONGRESS ID

CONGRESS TITLE

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

DATE and PLACE

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

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All Applications Have Undergone A Double-Blind Peer Review Process

PRESENTATION

Oral Presentation

INTERNATIONAL
MEDITERRANEAN
CONGRESS

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Proceedings Book

**LOW-COST ELECTROMECHANICAL RELAY: CONSTRUCTION TO UNDERSTAND
MAXWELL'S EQUATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL PURPOSES**

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Abstract

Electrical/electronic devices are present in various fields of human activity and have forever changed the way people live, work and communicate. In this way, providing entertainment, convenience, and information generally makes everyday life easier and more productive. All this technological advance achieved by electronics was only possible thanks to the efforts of several physical scientists, engineers, and inventors who dedicated themselves to discovering and creating mathematical and physical concepts that culminated in the creation of various electrical and electronic devices that contributed to scientific growth and providing better convenience for society. Among the many advances, we can highlight the creation of the incandescent lamp, the creation, and manipulation of electromagnetic waves, which later evolved with the creation of radio and television. However, this work aims to build a relay in order to better elucidate the physical concepts of electromagnetism applied to this device. Thus, it was necessary to study in order to understand the basic functioning of an electromechanical relay. Where, governed by Maxwell's second equation, also known as Ampere's Law. It is the current that flows through a conductor wire in which it generates a magnetic field, this magnetic field as far as it is concerned will have a sufficient magnetic force to attract a metallic contact, which makes this phenomenon be applied to a device, in this case the relay. After making the device using recyclable and low-cost materials, it was subjected to tests by means of a constant and increasing release of charges through a source, until it was possible for the coil to attract the metal plate. In this way, the use of Maxwell's equations in a practical and applied way was verified, opening a vast field of application possibilities for everyday use and at the same time it can be presented for educational purposes in the classroom.

Keywords: electronics devices, Ampere's Law, relay, confection, recyclable, educational purposes.